

ISic0194

I.Sicily inscription 0194

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

wedge-shaped interpunct according to Bivona and also clear in the photograph

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Dis M[an] [(ibus)]
2. Marciae · I, I [---]
3. piae · v(ixit) · a(nnis) · XX [---]
4. L(ucius) · Mammius · V [---]
5. uxori · cast[issimae]

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini with slight changes based on the photograph

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285221

EDR 127383

EDCS 22100121

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7419 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 117

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